

REPROCESSING OF MAGNESITE BENEFICIATION-WASTE TO RECOVER MINERAL VALUE AND MINIMISE ENVIRONMENTAL FOOTPRINT

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ABSTRACT. The current paper deals with the re-processing of mineralised mine waste from magnesite processing operations aiming at the recovery of the value. Two cases of mineralised waste were examined. First, waste derived from the removal of “fine” before hand-sorting, with particle size of -40 mm; this waste is usually stockpiled, comprises mostly of relatively coarse particles and is of relatively high-grade in magnesite. The separation methods applied were sorting, sink-float tests and magnetic separation. In general, the results from the application of physical separation methods were satisfactory. Commercial concentrates were obtained from sorting with MgCO₃-grade ranging between 94 and 97% MgCO₃ and yield about 46%; in case of mixing concentrate with middling, yield rises to 58-64% while grade slightly drops to 91-94%. Equally satisfactory were the results from sink-float separation at sp.gr. 2.88 (grade 95%, yield 45%) but questions arise from the small sp.gr. difference of magnesite and gangues. Finally, the less satisfactory results obtained from magnetic separation (grade around 80-85%, yield 33-65%) may be due to inefficient particles liberation and higher magnetic field is maybe required. Second, mineralised waste consisting of fine particles from size reduction operations were tested. These fines were processed with selective magnetic coating as well as co-agglomeration / magnetic separation techniques. In general, the results of physicochemical processing of fines were very encouraging both on single minerals and their artificial mixtures. In case of magnetic coating, the effect of pH, collector concentration and kerosene dose was studied first on single minerals. Optimum results were obtained for pH=9, dodecylamine solution 4.5x10⁻⁵ M and kerosene 2.5 L/t. Tests on artificial mineral mixtures at optimum conditions and magnetic separation at 0.8 A resulted in non-magnetic product with MgCO₃-grade higher than 99%. The parameters examined in co-agglomeration / magnetic separation tests were the same as with magnetic coating. Best conditions for co-agglomeration on single minerals were pH=8, dodecylamine 2 kg/t, kerosene 4 L/t. Tests on mineral mixture reveals that the MgCO₃-grade increases with dodecylamine but the yield drops.

Key words: magnesite, serpentine, waste, hydrophobic agglomeration.

Introduction

As human progress and economic prosperity strongly depend on mineral commodities, the need for continuously increasing demand of mineral raw materials results in equally increasing amounts of mineral commodities extraction and processing with subsequent generation of considerable amounts of waste rocks and tailings. Each year, billion tonnes of wastes and tailings are generated from various mining and processing activities, collectively called “extractive waste”. The amount of waste is different for each mineral commodity, ranging from some kilograms per kilogram of product for high-grade commodities (e.g. coal, bauxite, iron ores) to several million tonnes per tonne of product for low-grade or complex ores such as gold ores (EC-JRC, 2009; IAI, 2015). Only in EU, the amount of the total extractive waste generated in the period 2004-2014 roughly ranges between 550 and 750 Mt/year (Eurostat, 2015) while the estimation for the global extractive waste is over 100 billion tonnes per year (Rankin, 2015).

If not managed properly, the large volumes of extractive waste can have severe impacts on environment; consequently, proper management strategies are required both in short- and long-term (Adiansyah et al., 2015). Depending on their particle size and prior processing, these wastes are deposited in purpose-specific areas, known as Extractive Waste Facilities (EWF), either in the form of waste rock heaps or tailing dams. The listed EWFs in the EU-28 that are in operation, in the process of being closed, or abandoned amounted to about 9700 units (Garbarino et al., 2018). The increasing demand for mineral values leads to the extraction and processing of even lower-grade orebodies, the generation of greater quantities of very fine particles deposited as tailings and the corresponding

loss of mineral values, since separation methods are not very efficient for fines (Anastassakis, 2012). From the aforementioned, it derives that wastes are categorised into “mine waste”, which has no economic value and is rejected, and “mineralised mine waste”, which contains some quantity of mineral value and presents future potential economic prospects (Lottermoser, 2010). Consequently, the mineralised waste material could be considered a potential deposit for future mining and, after reprocessing, for value recovery (Anastassakis, 2002). This way of mining has several advantages over the traditional one, as less energy is required for extraction, transportation, reprocessing and recycling. In this way, extractive activities meet the fundamental principle of “recovery and recycling” and become more sustainable. The prerequisite for this consideration is the application of efficient reprocessing methods, the high-grade product and the positive overall economic outcome.

From the aforementioned, it is clear that extraction and mineral processing are unsustainable processes, since they create pollution and fail to entirely recover values, due to their fine particle size or their imperfect liberation from gangue. The current paper deals with the recovery of magnesite as a) coarse, rejected onto heaps and b) very fine particles, usually deposited into dams.

Magnesite is the most important mineral of magnesium. Especially for Greece, it constitutes one of the most important primary raw materials, being exploited and exported since many years ago as concentrate, caustic or caustic calcined magnesia (produced by magnesite heating to 620-680°C), and dead-burnt magnesia (produced by heating to a temperature

higher than 1450°C, usually at 1800°C or even more, and for longer time) (Dimopoulos, 2012).

Magnesite itself is mainly used in the production of fertilisers, but also electrodes and tiles as well. Caustic magnesia is used in the production of panels, industrial floors and abrasives, in pyro-metallurgy as desulfurising agent and flux, as well as in hydro-metallurgy, environmental protection, fuels additive, pharmaceuticals, etc., with the use being dependent on MgO grade. Dead-burnt magnesia is mainly used in the production of refractory mass for metallurgical applications, cement and chemical industry. The higher MgO content is, the better is the quality of dead-burnt magnesia and its refractory properties. The samples originate from Evia Island, on which the exploitation of magnesite initiated in 1893. A sorting stage was included as part of the entire flowsheet of the plant with prior discard of the “fine” ore particles (-40 mm) in heaps, not amenable to efficient sorting according to the industrial schedule but being mineralised waste. Till recently, the stockpiled mineralised waste was amounted to about 250000 tonnes, with a relatively high grade in magnesite mineral (about 50%).

The target of the current work is to investigate the possibility to produce a commercial magnesite concentrate from a) hand-sorting “fine” tailings using physical separation methods and b) from very fine particles lost in tailings not efficiently separated from gangue using selective agglomeration methods (magnetic coating, co-agglomeration).

Method and Materials

Case 1

The material used in the current work was the aforementioned -40 mm fraction that was removed as fine before industrial hand-sorting. Two representative samples were obtained; one with particle size -40+10 mm and another with -10+2.36 mm. The later sample was sieved into fractions as follows: -10+4.75 mm whose weight was 22% w/w of the total, -4.75+2.36 mm with 27% w/w and -2.36 mm with 51% w/w; each one submitted to the corresponding separation. The liberation degree of the initial samples ranged from 81% for the -40+10 mm fraction to 93% for the -2.36 mm.

The particles -40+10 mm and -10+4.75 mm were submitted to sorting; the fraction -2.36 mm was tested through sink-float analysis; finally, the fractions -10+4.75 mm, -4.75+2.36 mm, and -2.36 mm were submitted to magnetic separation tests. The results are presented in the next section (Dimopoulos, 2012).

Chemical analysis in MgCO₃ of the feed and products was based on CO₂ evolution using Differential Thermo-Gravimetric (DTG) and Differential Thermal Analysis (DTA). XRD and chemical analyses were carried out on representative samples ground to -0.075mm.

Case 2

In magnetic coating tests, the minerals originated from the initial samples after very careful hand-picking to collect as pure as possible particles for each case. XRD analysis showed that magnesite samples were pure while serpentine was mainly in the form of antigorite while chrysotile, talc and olivine were also detected in very small percentage. Finally, magnetite used for coating tests was of heavy media grade.

Each mineral used for magnetic tests was successively crushed in jaw and cone crusher to -3 mm and wet ground in porcelain ball mill with porcelain grinding media. The size of the minerals' particles for coating tests was -75+25 µm while that of magnetite was -5 µm. The particle size of each mineral was measured using particle size analyser Malvern Master Sizer SB.0D. Magnetic coating tests were carried out using a 200 mL beaker and a stirrer with plastic impeller to keep the particles in suspension. The procedure is described in details elsewhere (Anastassakis, 1999).

In co-agglomeration / magnetic separation tests, the origin of the materials was the same as before. Initially, tests were carried out using single mineral samples, collected by hand-sorting. Magnesite sample was macroscopically pure while the other, named “gangue”, was actually a mixture of various minerals. The XRD-analysis confirmed the purity of magnesite sample, as no impurities were detected; on the contrary, the gangue was composed of serpentine, ilmenite, and olivine as forsterite (Bimpilas and Anastassakis, 2016).

After preliminary experimentation, conditioning and settling time were maintained constant at 30 seconds each.

The tests on single minerals were carried out in a beaker of 400 mL. A total of 2 g-sample of magnesite or tailing was conditioned in 300 mL dodecylamine (DDA) solution of certain concentration. The pH of the suspension was regulated at the desired value and the suspension was conditioned for 3 min. Subsequently, only the gangue was submitted to wet high-intensity magnetic (WHIM) separation; the products of magnetic separation were collected, dried and weighted. In reference to the artificial mixture, the procedure was the same except the weight of the material that was 5 g of solid suspended in 750 mL of DDA solution. After conditioning, the mixture was fed to WHIM separator using a peristaltic pump. In this case, the MgCO₃ content of the products was determined by Thermal Gravimetric Analysis (TGA).

The reagents used in Case 2 were: DDA, NaOH and HCl solutions for pH adjustment, kerosene, and emulsifier when necessary. Both single minerals and artificial mixtures were used. The ratio of magnetite / serpentine was 50/50 in magnetic coating and magnetite / total gangue 75/25 in co-agglomeration.

Results and Discussion

Case 1

The -40 mm industrial waste was tested into hand-sorting, sink-float and magnetic separation. The results are presented below (Dimopoulos, 2012; Dimopoulos and Anastassakis, 2013).

Results of sorting

The metallurgical results of sorting are presented in Table 1. For process analysis reasons, three products (concentrate, middling, tailing) were obtained instead of two (concentrate, tailing), which is the usual case in electronic sorting. The products were analysed through TG analysis.

As regards the size fraction -40+10 mm (Table 1), a clearly marketable concentrate may be produced by sorting. In case of mixing middling with concentrate, the concomitant product is of slightly lower grade but it still remains marketable (higher than 90%) with MgCO₃ recovery approaching 91.5%.

Table 1. Results of sorting

Particle size mm	Product	Weight %	MgCO ₃ %	MgCO ₃ distribution %
-40+10	C*	47.2	93.7	75.9
	M	11.3	80.0	15.5
	C+M	58.5	91.1	91.4
	T	41.5	12.0	8.6
	F	100.0	58.2	100.0
-10+4.75	C	46.2	97.0	68.1
	M	18.4	85.2	23.9
	C+M	64.6	93.6	92.0
	T	35.4	15.0	8.0
	F	100.0	65.8	100.0

* C: Concentrate, M: Middling, T: Tailing, F: Feed

For particle size -10+4.75 mm, the grade of the concentrate increases to 97% MgCO₃, while the grade is slightly reduced to the equally marketable value of 93.6% MgCO₃ after mixing with middlings. The corresponding MgCO₃ recovery for the pure concentrate is 68.1% and increases to 92% by mixing middling with concentrate. Finally, the tailing may be rejected as it is, because of its low grade in MgCO₃. In case of merging concentrate and middling, the MgCO₃ losses to the tailing are only 8%. The successful separation is clearly denoted by the different colour of the products after microscopy examination (Figure 1).

(a)

(b)

Fig. 1. Photos of (a) the feed and (b) the products of sorting

Results of sink-float separation

The size fraction -2.36 mm was submitted to sink-float tests, given that magnesite particles are considerably liberated from gangue ones. Heavy liquid with sp.gr. 2.88 was used for the tests. The products were rinsed with ethanol and water, dried at 120 °C for 3 hours, weighted, ground to -0.075mm and chemically analysed using TG analysis (Table 2).

Table 2. Results of sink-float separation at sp.gr. 2.88

Product	Weight %	MgCO ₃ %	MgCO ₃ distribution %
Sink	45.07	95.0	72.2
Float	54.93	30.0	27.8
Feed	100.00	59.28	100.0

The results clearly show that magnesite separation from tailings is feasible at this sp. gr., since a commercial grade concentrate of 45% yield and 95% MgCO₃ is obtained. On the other hand, the small difference in sp. gr. between magnesite and gangue minerals (magnesite 2.98, dolomite 2.84, serpentine 2.60) denotes that there might be difficulties with respect to their separation by gravity methods. This is sustained by the relatively high grade of the tailings in magnesite and the losses of magnesite in the tailings.

Results of magnetic separation

The equipment used for magnetic separation was a drum separator with permanent magnet. The results of magnetic separation are presented in Table 3.

Table 3. Results of magnetic separation

Particle size mm	Product	Weight %	MgCO ₃ %	MgCO ₃ distr. %
-10+4.75	NM*	64.9	84.8	92.4
	M	35.1	12.8	7.6
	F	100.0	59.5	100.0
-4.75+2.36	NM	62.8	80.5	89.9
	M	37.2	15.3	10.1
	F	100.0	56.2	100.0
-2.36	NM	33.5	86.8	59.2
	M	66.5	30.0	40.8
	F	100.0	49.0	100.0

*NM: Non-magnetic, M: Magnetic, F: Feed

From this Table, it is clear that the results are generally inferior in comparison to hand-sorting and sink-float tests. More specifically, a non-magnetic concentrate of marginally commercial grade can be produced only for particles -2.36 mm. In addition to its relatively low quality, this product has also a very low yield and MgCO₃ recovery.

The grade of the fraction -10+4.75 mm is slightly less than the commercial but its recovery in MgCO₃ is high. In regard to the particles -4.75+2.36 mm, the grade of the concentrate is the lowest among the three size fractions but the recovery in MgCO₃ is high enough. The comparison of magnetic separation to the other methods reveals that, in general, the yield of the concentrate is higher but the grade is lower, which could be attributed to the existence of non-magnetic minerals (e.g., dolomite, talc) in the magnesite concentrate.

XRD analysis of the magnetics for particles -2.36 mm detected magnesite, sepiolite, serpentine, talc (possibly non-liberated from magnetic minerals), and amphibole.

Case 2

This case refers to the separation of fine magnesite particles from similar size gangue. The generation of fine

particles is inevitable in many processing operations of mineral commodities. Especially in cases of low-grade ores, the value mineral has to be ground to very fine size to achieve high liberation degree, because of its finely disseminated form and mineralogical texture. The separation of fine mineral particles presents considerable difficulties, because of the peculiar properties of fine particles (Fuerstenau et al., 1979). Due to these properties, a lot of effort has been devoted to their separation through physicochemical methods which are primarily based on the modification or combination of standard separation methods, such as flotation (Rulyov, 2016; Hoang et al., 2021; Sajjad and Otsuki, 2022), agglomeration or combination of agglomeration with flotation (Anastassakis, 2012; Yang et al., 2016). In the current work the results of magnetic coating and agglomeration / magnetic separation are employed.

Results of magnetic coating - discussion

Figure 2 shows the magnetic separation of single minerals (magnesite, serpentine) after their conditioning with magnetite in the presence of DDA.

As it derives, the recovery of fine serpentine particles to the magnetic product is almost complete throughout the entire pH range between 6 and 11, which denotes that serpentine particles obtained a magnetic coating by controlling the surface properties of serpentine and magnetite fine particles. Microscopic examination of serpentine particles after coating reveals that they obtained a strong magnetic coating (Figure 3). The magnetic coating occurred not only on single particles but also on agglomerates of serpentine particles.

Fig. 2. Recovery of single minerals through magnetic separation with pH after magnetic coating

The results of Figure 2 denote that magnesite practically obtains no magnetic coating till pH=9.

This is confirmed by Figure 3b, which shows the results for pH=6. For pH>9, the coating of the surface of magnesite particles increased with pH but, even in the very basic pH region, the percentage of the magnetically-rendered magnesite was less than 20%.

Microscopic examination of magnesite particles after coating revealed that, in any case, the magnetic coat was much less extended and less strongly attached than in the case of serpentine.

Fig. 3. Photos of serpentine (a) and magnesite (b) after magnetic coating at pH=6

The addition of kerosene resulted in stronger and tighter serpentine coating.

After single minerals, tests with artificial mixtures (1.0 g of each mineral) at selected pH values followed, the results of which are presented in Figures 4a-c. As observed, the grade of the non-magnetic product in magnesite is higher than 99% while the participation of serpentine is less than 0.8% (Figures 4a and c) with a recovery of $MgCO_3$ higher than 92% for pH lower than 8, slightly dropping to 88% for pH=10. Similarly, the $MgCO_3$ grade of the magnetic product is relatively low, ranging between 6 and 11%. The aforementioned findings denote that the results with artificial mixtures are slightly inferior to those on single minerals but they are equally satisfactory with those of single minerals.

Results of agglomeration / magnetic separation - discussion

In these tests, the effect of pH and DDA dose was examined. Conditioning time was kept constant at 3 min, settling time at 30 sec and agitation speed at 210 rpm. The effect of pH was studied with DDA dose of 1 kg/t while that of DDA dose at pH=8.

The dependence of hydrophobic agglomeration with pH is shown in Figure 5. As observed, the weight of the settled co-agglomerated gangue (mixture of serpentine, ilmenite, olivine) is much higher than that of magnesite throughout the entire pH range 7 to 11, remaining practically constant (around 78%). For magnesite, no agglomeration practically occurs in the slight alkaline region (pH=7-9) while the weight of the settled mineral

increases for pH=10-11, but it remains much lower than that of gangue (max 8.5% at pH=11).

a

b

c

Fig. 4. (a) yield of non-magnetic product, grade and recovery in MgCO₃, (b) yield of magnetic product, grade and recovery in MgCO₃, (c) yield of non-magnetic product, grade and recovery in serpentine

Consequently, selective hydrophobic agglomeration of gangue with the use of DDA seems feasible for pH = 7-9.

Microscopic observation of the settled products at pH=8 reveals that magnesite is encountered either as single particles or small clusters of weakly-held agglomerates (Figure 6a), while the fine particles of the gangue mineral mixture have formed relatively large and strong agglomerates (Figure 6b).

Fig. 5. Effect of pH on hydrophobic agglomeration of minerals

(a)

(b)

Fig. 6. Settled (a) single magnesite particles, (b) agglomerated gangue (DDA 1 kg/t)

Magnetic separation tests on the agglomerated gangue mixture revealed that a relatively high percentage (between 75-85%) was allocated to the magnetics. This is due to the co-agglomeration of all the three gangue minerals, out of which at least ilmenite possesses strong magnetic properties while serpentine and olivine possess weak to non-magnetic properties. Consequently, these clusters are attracted by the magnetic field. Microscopic examination of the products revealed that the magnetic product was mostly composed of relatively large-size gangue co-agglomerates while the non-magnetic gangue was composed of much smaller size, loosely held agglomerates or even single gangue particles.

The effect of DDA dose on the agglomeration of single minerals was investigated next, for DDA additions of up to 2.0 kg per tonne of mineral (Figure 7). The results clearly show that magnesite is slightly affected for DDA additions lower than 2 kg/t; on the contrary, the weight of the agglomerated gangue

continuously increases with DDA dose, reaching to approximately 86% for DDA 2.0 kg/t of mineral.

Microscopic observations, not presented here, reveal that the settled gangue (serpentine, ilmenite, and olivine mixture) is comprised of co-agglomerated fine particles in all cases. Also, the increase of DDA addition results in stronger and larger size agglomerates. On the contrary, magnesite fine particles are mostly encountered as single particles or loose agglomerates.

The addition of kerosene along with DDA 2 kg/t, at pH=8, had a comparatively stronger impact on magnesite than on gangue, as the weight of the settled product increased significantly to about 15% (compared to about 8.5% without kerosene). The weight of the settled gangue increased to 94% (compared to 85.9% without kerosene) but the addition of kerosene resulted in tighter gangue agglomerates than using DDA only.

After experimentation on single minerals, tests were carried out on magnesite / gangue artificial mixtures of 3 / 1 ratio and DDA / kerosene mixtures of 2 / 1 ratio with varying DDA dose (Figure 8). As shown, the increase of DDA dose is beneficial to magnesite concentrate (non-magnetic), as its grade increases gradually from 75% (feed) to approximately 95%, which means improvement of the feed grade by 25%. In reference to recovery, there is a gradual drop with amine addition but it still remains satisfactory.

Fig. 7. Effect of DDA addition on the weight of settled material

Fig. 8. Effect of DDA dose on non-magnetic product after agglomeration / magnetic separation of artificial mineral mixture

Conclusions

As mineral deposits extraction has shifted to even lower grades and mine waste volumes are even larger, the recovery of the initially discarded value mineral, under favourable technical and economic circumstances, will render mining more sustainable by saving resources from rapid depletion, securing resources for future generations, reducing energy consumption for extraction, saving water for ore processing and reducing areas for waste disposal.

This work deals with the recovery of magnesite from waste, deposited in waste heaps, by applying traditional physical separation methods for the coarse and physicochemical (magnetic coating and co-agglomeration / magnetic) separation techniques for the fines.

The results in both cases proved satisfactory and may be applied in other cases as well. In more details:

- Among the physical methods tested (sorting, sink-float tests and magnetic separation), the most efficient proved sorting. Commercial concentrates were obtained from sorting of high $MgCO_3$ -grade (between 94 and 97% $MgCO_3$) and yield about 46%. The yield can be improved to 58-64% by merging the concentrate with middling but the grade slightly drops (to 91-94%). Regarding sink-float separation, the results are equally satisfactory at sp.gr. 2.88, as the grade of the sink product was high enough (95% $MgCO_3$) and the yield 45%; however, the separation by gravity method seems very difficult, if not impossible, because of the small difference in sp.gr. between magnesite and gangues. Finally, less satisfactory results are obtained from magnetic separation (grade around 80-85%, yield 33-65%), which could be attributed to the inefficient particles liberation. The application of stronger magnetic field could improve the results. In general, the results from the application of physical separation methods are considered satisfactory.
- As great portion of mineralised waste derives from operations of size reduction to fine particle size and the problem is expected to be more intense with the extraction of even lower grade ores, the second series of tests was carried out on fine particles by applying physicochemical methods. These fines were processed with selective magnetic coating as well as co-agglomeration / magnetic separation techniques. Tests were carried out both on single minerals and their mixture. In case of magnetic coating, the effect of pH, collector concentration and kerosene dose was studied first on single minerals. Optimum results were obtained for pH = 9, dodecylamine solution 4.5×10^{-5} M and kerosene 2.5 L/t. Tests on artificial mineral mixtures at optimum conditions and magnetic separation at 0.8 A resulted in non-magnetic product with $MgCO_3$ -grade higher than 99%. The parameters examined in co-agglomeration / magnetic separation tests were the same as with magnetic coating. Best conditions for co-agglomeration on single minerals were pH=8, dodecylamine 2 kg/t, kerosene 4 L/t. Tests on mineral mixture reveal that the $MgCO_3$ -grade increases with dodecylamine but the yield drops. In general, the results of physicochemical processing of fines were very encouraging both on single minerals and their artificial mixtures. Considering the complex physicochemical

behaviour of magnesite, the results are also very promising for further application to other mineral systems.

In summary, the reprocessing and recovery of value from mineralised waste, where possible, should enhance the overall extraction economics and reduce the environmental impacts from mineralised waste rejection, making mineral extraction and processing operations more sustainable.

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